

USE OF THEONYM IN FOLKLORE TEXTS

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Annotation. This article describes the views on the use of theonyms in folklore texts. Different forms of theonyms in Uzbek folk proverbs, folk songs and epics have been analyzed. The specific characteristics of theonyms have been revealed.

Key words: theonyms, folklore text, religious text, mythonym, epic.

Theonyms are very ancient lexical units in the language, the periods of their emergence are related to the religious views of humanity in the ancient world, animism, totemism, taboo, euphemism, and other ideas. The emergence of theonyms went through periods of polytheism and monotheism.

"Theonym" (Greek theog god (Allah) + onoma proper noun) means the proper noun of God's name and attributes. "Theonymy" is a collection, sum of such famous nouns, "theonymy" means the field that studies proper nouns belonging to such an onomastic scope. The information found in the works of scientists such as G.P.Snesaryov, O.A.Sukhareva, N.Direnkova, M.V.Stebleva, T.D.Bayaliyeva, N.F.Mokshin about Turkic theonims, especially its history in ancient times, is valuable. For example, in the article of G.P. Snesaryov, the ancient deities of Arabian tribes are al-Lot, al-Uzzo, Manot; Yemenite deities Wadd, Suva'; Ramuza, Ahraman, Ahura-Mazda belonging to ancient history, as well as dragons, giants (devoh), fairies, demons related to mythical images, their genesis, etymology are discussed [1]. Allah (God), Khudoy, God, Creator, Yazdon, deity, goddesses and attributes related to these concepts are observed in historical, artistic, ethnographic, folkloristic, mythological, partially linguistic sciences, but the concept of theonym, theonymy, its boundaries and scope. There are no consistent opinions about the exact lexical onomastic units, their boundaries and scope.

Many theonims are also found in Uzbek folklore texts, not only Islamic theonims, but general theonims are often referred to, and views of ordinary people's faith in different periods are clearly expressed.

For example, in the proverb "Father is pleased - God is pleased", the greatness of the father is expressed through the theonym of God, while in the proverb "The

light of loneliness is God" it is said that a person should never be depressed in loneliness. goes

"If he is right, there is no problem,
When the truth curses, there is no cure."

"It means God,

A person riding a camel crosses the mountain" [2, B.25]-and in these proverbs
It refers to the greatness of God Almighty.

In Uzbek folk songs, the gods of the polytheistic period names are cited:

"A silent woman is a swimming woman
Shadow field woman.

Let the rain be oil, let it be a lake,

May the earth and the world be wet."

The image of Sus woman in this text is found among Central Asian, Caucasian and other peoples; She was also known as the word woman, the milk woman, the water woman, and she was considered the god of rain, and this song was sung in the rituals of summoning rain [3, B.116].

In Uzbek nomenclature, in the following years, terms such as "mythonym", "myfozonym", "myphotonym", "myphophytonym", "myphoanthronym" are also used. For example, in the system of images of Uzbek mythology, beliefs about mythical birds also play an important role. Ango is one of such imaginary, mythological birds. In many folklore works, that is, all birds are imagined as a mythical ancestor or mother. There are also mythological views that the ango is a legendary bird that lives in Kohi Qaf, the king of all birds. In some Uzbek folk tales, ango appears as a mythological creature similar to the image of symbolic birds. In general, the image of anko is one of the common artistic elements of the epic genres of Uzbek folklore (such as myth, legend, fairy tale, epic), and the religious views of our people about this bird are mythological and epic interpretations. as deeply embedded in folklore works. It should be noted that the image of "anqo" has been used as an artistic symbol in many works in Uzbek classical literature under the direct influence of the artistic traditions of folk art.

In epics, which are the largest type of folklore texts, we can find many theonyms.

For example, in the epic "Alpomish", "Boysari stood up and said: "If we can't take it, if we can't buy it, if God doesn't give it, where will we get it from?!" Boybori said: "From here, the river of Shahimardan Pir is three kilometers away. while everyone goes and spends the night: the state demands the stateAs long as he wishes for children, as he wishes for faith in the end, he who spends the night for forty days

will return to his will. If we also go, if we give our prayers, if we spend the night at Shahimardan Pir's tomb and wish for a child."

Or another example:

"...This shunt was lying in a drunken sleep,

He saw the Prophet.

The Prophet said these words: if we wish for a child"

Or another example:

"...This shunker was lying in a drunken sleep, and he saw the Messenger of God. The Messenger of God said these words: "My erring Ummah, I am Your Compassionate One. "Don't be sad, my ummah, said the prophet, Underneath is the duldul, on the waist is Zulfiqar, In his bridle, Baba Qambar is the bridle, In your sorrow, Shahimardan pirs rode."

In the given fragments, the theonyms: God, Shahimardan pir, ravza, iman, nazr-u niyaz, rasul, prophet, ummah, Baba Qambar are used, and through these symbols the faith and trust of the heroes are shown [4,B. 12].

In excerpts from another folk epic "Birth of Goroguli":

"The king is the real God himself. The king of these is a creature created by the figurative God. God also made them kings. For this reason, if the citizen insults the figurative king, the real king is bitter and God is pleased. It was not pleasing to God that Holmon, without taking the words of the minister, came arrogantly without looking at the Yeovmites, saying: "I will immediately kill the Yeovmites, take their land, loot their property, and destroy their women." Another example:

"God's work no more,

How much dust do I pass at night?

Dear sister, I said, Hilolay,

Go, I'll take you to Yovmit!"

"It was night. Bibi Hilal read the night prayer, put the kalam rabbon around her neck saying, "I am being killed by Shahdar Khan", and prayed to God for her death: "I am in the hands of Shahdar Khan's men. "Don't help me, do whatever you want to do yourself," he begged God, invoked the intercession of all the prophets and the past saints, and wept. passed".

"Mighty Maulana, who is kind to everyone, I wandered in the hands of Zargar. If you are an uncle, tell me, my descendants,

Tell me about my seed, uncle!" In these passages, Allah Almighty is God, Haq, Khaliq, Maulana theonims are used synonymously, and theonims Khufton, Namaz, Kalomi Rabbani gave the hero of the work an Islamic spirit.

They gathered in the streets saying, "We will be emperors of all countries" and went to receive blessings from the idols of Lot, Manot, the golden prophet, and the silver chahor.

"Even though Bibi Hilal died, her child did not die. By the grace of God, she was in the womb. At that moment, she wanted to give birth. Eve, Anbar, and Fatma came."

"All abdal, avtar, forty chiltans took one by one. Hazrat Khizr also said my child."

In these passages, theonym names such as Lot, Manot, Eve, Anbar ena, Fatma buvi, and Hazrat Khizr are widely used.

"This house goes to the grave every day. Let's enjoy it. What will he do when he goes to the grave?" they said. Shuytib is a thirty-year-old manthey came to the cemetery lurking behind the temple. Then a lion, who was lying in the cemetery, jumped at the boy. Then Hazrat Khizr came and slapped the lion. "The lion was squirming."

"Looking like that, big mosques, madrasahs, minarets were seen in several places inside the city."

"He puts good leaders in the streets,
The mosque-madrassa is in your mind,
Introducing the Lashkari Komat,
Everyone prays in congregation.
The reward will fly to the sky,
He will deliver his reward to Arsh-u Kursi,
A citizen sleeps in a mosque,
The bruised maple is the name of Haq,
Every citizen will be a Muslim.
This is the meaning of your dream, Shahdar Khan.

In the above passages, theonyms of places such as mazar, ghoristan, mazaristan, mosques, madrasahs, Arsh-u Kursi are given.

"Get off your horse, you bastards,
Iranians who have traveled the Maghreb, Mashriq,
May the ghost of Hilalo be with you,
I gave it to God, Allahu Akbar." [5]

In the given four, the name of the Islamic concept forms the text of the prayer. Such examples are very common in Uzbek folklore texts, and these theonyms form the basis of theo-linguistics

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